

Original Research Article

The Culture of Dialog and the Role of Primary School Leaders In Promoting It: Case study of Al-Ras Educational District

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Abstract

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The study aims at getting to know the culture of dialog and the role of primary school leaders in promoting it. Case study: Al-Ras Educational district. The community under investigation covered all primary school leaders during the second semester of the school year (2019/2020), which consisted of 206 leaders. The sample study was randomly selected, consisting of 150 subject. To achieve the objectives of this study, a questionnaire was developed covering (50) paragraphs unfolded into two areas. The study came up with the following results: the role of school leaders in promoting a culture of dialog among primary school students was moderate. Moreover, there were statistically significant differences between the sample estimates' means, attributed to gender, in favor of females. there were no differences attributed to experience.

Keywords: Al-Ras district, Dialog culture, Primary school students, School leaders

INTRODUCTION

Educators agree that dialog brings people together and improves the language of human relationship which stems from a human innate need of being drawn toward his counterparts. this relationship resulting from communication and dialog would disrupt any negative perception of difference and diversity and keeps it within its conventional limits. if no communication and dialog between individuals or groups existed, emotional deficiency would become a suitable ground for hatred (Al-Safar, 2004).

Debate is considered to be one of the most important communicative tools amongst peoples and nations for gap reduction and views convergence and therefore, improving progress, sophistication and prosperity. Dialog is regarded as one of the most crucial bases for social life. For it is the tool through which the human expresses their desires, feelings, tendencies and internal needs, notwithstanding it being a tool for self improvement. Also, it is indisputable for the individual who tends to argue

and communicate with others to have a set of language and dialog skills, be it listening, talking, reading or writing (Farouq, 2009).

Dialog is a human language needed for communication, meeting of minds, visualization unity and perspectives convergence. A positive debate requires some fundamentals like the admission of the existence of the other stance and the right of having a different view as well as finding the truth regardless to he who found it. The significance of dialog also shows in the exchange of points of view between debaters, which leads each one of them to know the other point of view and therefore know the truth or spread awareness amongst people in all domains. To make any dialog successful and to attain its goals, it is a must for the debaters to adhere to the ethical, cultural and sociobehavioral standards. (Qotnany; 2010)

Dialog is defined as the conversation between two or more parties, by means of question and answer, on the

condition of thematic unity or purpose integrity. They run the discussion on a specific matter, may reach a result and one may not convince the other, but the listener grabs the moral and manufactures a stance for himself (Al-Zumkhashry, 2001). In 2004, Al-Maghamisi defined it as: "a kind of conversation between two people or two groups, in which the exchange of words between them is done in an equal manner, and one of them is not exclusively excluded by the other. It is governed by calmness away from any rivalry or intolerance." (p. 34). While Al-Halibi (2009: 41) defines it as "verbal and non-verbal interaction between two or more, with a purpose of communicating and exchanging ideas, feelings and experiences." Each of which, under the umbrella globalization and multiculturalism (Mahjub, 2006).

There is a global tendency to the culture of dialog and its spread at all levels in societies, by laying the foundations, developing and supporting and spreading it as well as finding a proper place for it in the educational systems, leading to achieve coexistence, harmony and integration internally and externally between members of one society, and to bring people together. It is, in fact, from here where the importance of the culture of dialogue and its required skills among members of society shows by means of the social and educational institutions. On top of them comes the school at all levels, which contributes to enhance the culture of dialog and its skills within the students, and therefore, discover his mental and emotional maturity which grants their interaction with the individuals within the community to which they belong. The dialog is concerned with developing the competencies of the individual to listen effectively to the others and understand what they say, analyse and examine their speech, in light of the information and experiences he has on the target topic (Awad, 2009).

Because school is one of the most important institutions in the society, it is one of the highlights to be considered in inculcating the culture of dialog, since it is the best way to communicate as well as the most effective element to a successful educational process in the first place, as it works to establish links and relations between all the operators of the educational process, all within a framework prevailed with love and mutual respect. In addition to its contribution to learning and understanding, as well as consolidating information in the minds of students, in an appropriate manner, within an atmosphere of suspense and competition (Hamouri, 2011).

Also since the school leader is the one who leads the school with its teachers, workers and students towards the desired aims in light of the philosophy of the community to which the school belongs, and in light of the message and vision of the Ministry of Education. Thus, he is the responsible and supervisor of all the areas of the educational learning process at school, the caretaker and the guide for students as well as the controller to all teachers in all technical matters

related to the teaching process, dialog also serves as a channel of communication between the school and the local community, in addition to its role in spreading love and understanding among all members of the school, and in fostering a culture of dialogue, which is reflected in the school, family and society (Boscardin, McCarthy and Delgado, 2009; Al-Hariri, 2010).

The significance of the culture of dialog in the educational learning process and its role shows in enabling students to confront what may face them, as holding different views, which is quite normal in the modern world, where opinions differ. Based on the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia 2030 and what the importance of this vision, its aims and objectives emphasize which are directly concerned with the student in all his intellectual, physical and emotional aspects in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. This study, therefore, came to identify the role of school leaders in fostering a culture of debate among students in the Al-Ras educational district schools.

One last study to wrap up with was operated by Al-Mizer (2017) aimed to identify the role of the family in promoting a culture of dialog. A social survey was distributed on a purposively selected sample, which comprised of 253 subjects from the Ministry of Education in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. This study was based on a questionnaire measuring three dimensions to achieve the overall goal of the study. The results showed that the first dimension: *learning the basics of dialog in the Saudi family* ranked high. Also, among the most important challenges that the results showed are:

The attachment to social media and the intolerance with criticism during the dialog. The study also found that the third dimension which is related to the set of proposals to promote a culture of dialog within the Saudi family ranked high. Finally, the study was enriched with a set of suggestions which would help promote a culture of dialog within the Saudi family, such as: Inculcating the principles of dialog within children from a very young age, and encouraging the families to use the effective dialog.

Research Problem

Numerous studies, such as Martorana's (2003)'s, Kenefick's (2004), and Hamouri's (2011) indicated that dialog leads to form a more thoughtful, effective and aware student. As it contributes to strengthen the student-student and teacher-student relationships, as well as enables them to express their true feelings. In addition, dialog has a primary role in achieving communication, acquaintance and exchange between individuals, societies, peoples and civilizations, and in the exchange of dialogs in the classroom.

To establish a culture of dialog in school management between the director and students at school, the school leader should be in mutual trust with those he talks to, by

respecting and appreciating them. Also, it is recommended for the school leader to represent a good example so that the dialog can be effective for students as they are attentive to what he says and what he does. With being disciplined and into the bargain, he can be a good role model for the students (Al-Manjara, 2005).

In order for the dialog to be fruitful between the school's administration and the students, the school leader must be aware of the school's goals and responsibilities, and the powers of each member, which should be clear to all, so that everyone can perform his duties and get his rights and the dialog is built upon clear and correct information (Alabid, 2008).

As a former school leader for almost two decades, a faculty member at Tibba University and a current teacher of school leaders at the PhD and Masters degrees, and a supervision of Masters' projects in the field of education, the researcher observed a weakness in the culture of dialog. In order to discover the reality, the study came to identify the culture of dialog and the role of primary school leaders in promoting it.

Research Questions

Taking place at Al-Ras region, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What role do school leaders play in fostering the culture of dialog among primary school students in Al-Ras educational region?
2. Do the estimates of the study sample's subjects on fostering the culture of dialog among primary school students in Al-Ras region vary by the variables (sex, experience)?

Research Aims

This study aims to:

1. reveal the role of school leaders in promoting the culture of dialog among students of Al-Ras region's schools.
2. uncover the differences between the estimates of the study's sample on promoting a culture of dialog according to the variables (gender, experience).

Significance of the Study

The importance of the study is shown in:

- giving more insights about the culture of dialog to the human knowledge as well as The Arabian Academic world in general, and The Saudi bibliography in specific.
- uncovering the role of school leaders in promoting a culture of dialog among the students.
- informing decision makers in Al-Ras educational area about the role of school leaders in promoting a culture of

dialog among primary school students for its development and advancement.

Research Terms

Role: a prescribed function or behavior performed especially in a particular operation within a group or organization. A model of an individual's social behavior in relation to the group's social and cultural environment, as well as a form of response to what others expect from the individual" (Al-Shubul and Al-Khawalida, 2014: 62).

A working definition of the term can be a set of practices performed by the school leader, because of the nature of his work in promoting the culture of dialog among school students. It is measured by the response of the sample to the tool used for the purposes of study.

Culture of Dialog: The process in which the possibilities of an effective dialog with the other part are present, the belief in their existence and rights, the maintenance of the flow of information, the exchange of speech between the two parties, and the understanding of the nature, objectives and deficiencies of dialog" (Al-Obaid, 2009: 32).

Limitations of the Study

- Spatial limitations: the study was limited to Al-Ras district's schools.
- Objective limitations: to recognize the role of school leaders in promoting a culture of dialog among students.
- Temporal limitations: the first term of the school year: 1441(AH)/ 2019-2020(CE).
- Human limitations: The sample of the study was limited to primary school leaders in Al-Ras district.

Previous Studies

Previous studies on the role of school leaders in promoting a culture of dialog among students were examined through research in past literature and undergraduate studies, in addition to a number of Arabic and foreign studies, some of which are presented below:

Previous Studies

Artorana (2003) conducted a study aimed at identifying the role of exchanging spoken messages in high school classrooms which tackled the educational atmosphere in Britain. In so doing, the researcher followed an analytical approach, analyzing 175 dialogs which happened among 15 students with each other and with their teachers. The study revealed that the exchange of talk messages in the

classroom contributed in ameliorating the relationship between the students .

In a similar study, Kenefick (2004) investigated the impact of dialog in education at all levels in the American State-Boston in terms of: research, application and evaluation. To realize this, the researcher prepared a creative thinking program using the in-school dialog process. The results showed that dialog leads to produce a more intellectual, effective and conscious student.

In 2010, Baskas conducted a study aimed at investigating teachers' ability to use dialog, and students' ability to understand the importance of dialog in learning in the American State of Minnesota. The study sample was composed of three groups of teachers and one group of students. A descriptive analytical approach was adopted in order to fulfill the study goals. The results revealed that dialog takes many forms, because it is used in group interactions, in technology, as well as in teacher-supervisor communication. Moreover, a diversity in teachers' use of the dialog style, a desire and acceptance of the dialog style by students, and that dialog is an important aspect in the classroom could be clearly noticed. And that the absence of differences in the management of dialog is attributed to the variable of experience.

By the same token, Hamouri (2011) conducted a study aimed at understanding the concept of dialog and culture, and indicating the role of school administration, teachers and curriculum in establishing a culture of dialog in Jordan schools. In the process, a descriptive approach was adopted by collecting data from different sources . The results of the study showed that the culture of dialog is: a rhetorical interaction based on a set of conventional customs and behavioral traditions, in which dialog plays a key role in achieving communication, knowledge and exchange between individuals, communities, peoples and civilizations. Furthermore, the main source of the culture of dialog is likely to be the Holy Quran and the Noble Sunnah through the clarity of its objectives, types of dialog and its rules. Besides, the educational insights stem from the Quran and the Sunnah. Finally, that the school has a great role in fostering a culture of dialog through: school administrations, teachers and curriculum.

Likewise, Al-Zahrani (2011) carried out a study to identify the degree to which the educational supervision's contribution helps to spread the culture of dialog from the point of view of the educational supervisors themselves and the teachers in MeccaCity - Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The sample of the study consisted of (65) educational supervisor and (536) female teacher. The data was collected through a questionnaire. The results of the study showed that the level of the dialog culture among the educational supervisors from the point of view of female educational supervisors and teachers regarding each aspect of the dialog was at an intermediate level.

Al-Anzi (2011), through his study, aimed to identify the responsibility of secondary school teachers in developing

the educational dialog skills among students, and the obstacles that prevent teachers from developing dialogue skills in HafrAl-Batin schools in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study sample consisted of (37) director, and (1101) teacher. A questionnaire was used as a tool to collect data. As a result, the study showed that teachers believe in the importance of educational dialog with students and encourage students to engage in dialogs, as they believe they_ teachers_ represent successful dialog examples within the classroom. Additionally, teachers address students' problems using a method of dialog treatment. He also directs the school radio to address discussable issues, and encourages students to issue posters that broadcast the concept of educational dialog among students, and seeks to raise the level of critical thinking in extra-curricular activities.

Equally important, another study was conducted by Al-Jararaa (2012), which aimed at proposing a strategy to develop a culture of dialog among the directors of schools in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. The study sample consisted of all directors of the government schools in the three territories of education in Jordan. A questionnaire was used as a tool to collect data. The study indicated that the practice of dialogue culture among school directors is at a high level, and that there are no statistically significant differences in the practice of dialogue culture attributed to the variable of gender.

In another study, Al-Shethry (2012) conducted a theoretical work aimed at identifying the feasibility of dialog and its usability in the family environment as a modern educational method with Islamic origins, and the role of dialog in solving various family problems. This study divulged that dialogue contributes in solving many family problems related to spouses, children , neighbors and relatives. As it also showed that many of these problems arise mostly and are aggravated due to the lack of dialogue, its misuse, or the lack of proficiency of its art on what is necessary to its success.

Sokr's study (2013) aimed to make known the degree to which the faculty members of media colleges and their counterparts in Palestinian universities play their role in promoting a culture of dialogue among their students from the students' own viewpoint. A descriptive analytical method was adopted for this research, relying on a couple of tools: a questionnaire and a personal interview. Applied to a stratified random sample consisting of (315) male and female students from media colleges and their counterparts in the Palestinian universities in the governorates of Gaza, the results showed that the vocal side weighed indisputably heavy, and that the aspect of body language obtained relatively the least part of attention. The study also emphasized the important role of faculty members according to the study sample responses. In addition, there are statistically significant differences between the means of the study sample estimates for the role of faculty members in promoting a culture of dialogue attributed to the variable *gender* in

favor of females. But, there are no statistically significant differences between the means of the study sample estimates for the role of faculty members in promoting the culture of dialogue attributed to the variables of *place of residence* and *university*.

Al-Jahimi (2013) carried out a study aimed at revealing Sharia sciences teachers's practice of dialog skills with their students of the intermediate level in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia from the point of view of the educational administrators and supervisors. The study sample consisted of (33) educational supervisor and (48) middle school directors working in The General Administration of Education in Riyadh, and was randomly selected. For data collection, a questionnaire was designed to include (30) paragraphs, distributed on four focal points. Of the several results this study attained, the most important was that the average practice of dialogue between Sharia teachers and their students was weak in terms of interpersonal dialog skills.

Al-Tamimi and Al-Tamimi (2014) conducted a theoretical study aimed to shed light on the culture of dialog and how to enhance it, what are its educational and social effects in Islamic societies. To achieve this, the study adopted a descriptive analytical approach in order to explore the concept of dialog culture, its manners, controls, constraints and areas. The study showed that there is some cognitive tenor related to the concept of dialog in Islam, which makes it a sophisticated way of communication and cross pollination within the methodological controls that achieve the purpose and value of dialog. It also revealed that spreading the culture of dialogue and learning its fundamentals helps to make this culture a daily behavior among the members of society. Notwithstanding its positive educational and social influence on the individual and society, including: building the personality, creating a generation capable of bearing responsibility and burdens of life, so that the individual becomes a positively active member in the community.

Al-Rumi (2014), too, conducted a study aimed at explaining the importance of defining the cognitive and national reasons for enhancing the culture of dialogue among middle and high school students from the teachers' point of view in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The study sample consisted of (349) teachers from the middle level, and (304) teachers from the secondary school level. A special questionnaire was distributed to them to define the knowledge and national motives required to enhance the culture of dialog. The study concluded that the necessary requirements to enhance the culture of dialog among middle and high school students, whether material or moral requirements such as: providing an environment conducive to establishing dialogues within the school by the administration and teachers, in addition to providing schools with the needed materials and the necessary equipments to help spread the culture of dialogue. Finally, the study highlighted the need to

practice dialog and encourage its practice by the school administration and teachers in the middle and secondary levels.

Shaqoura (2015) conducted a study that aimed to identify the impact of enriching the content of the Civil Education Book in developing the values of dialog among the students of the fourth grade in Gaza City, Palestine. The sample of the study was composed of two groups, an experimental group of (40) students, and a control group of (40) students. A list of dialog values was prepared within the fourth grade book, and a test was designed in order to realize the study. The study showed that the content of the fourth grade civic education book included (371) value, the content of the fourth grade civic education book was enriched by the values of dialog that seemed to receive the lowest order in the analysis: Personality strength, patience, proof of evidence, honesty in presentation, turn taking respect, self-confidence. The results also showed that there were statistically significant differences between the means of the students of the experimental and control groups in the test in favor of the experimental group.

Al Jabreen (2016) conducted a study aimed at exploring the cultural background of the concept of dialog among teachers, and discovering the role of the school environment in promoting students' culture of dialog, as well as identifying the obstacles to promoting this culture. To achieve these goals, a descriptive approach was adopted, and a questionnaire was designed for a research tool. The study sample was made up of (620) high school teachers in Suwaidi City of Riyadh, but the questionnaire was only distributed to 125 subject. The study revealed that the cultural background of the concept *dialog* among teachers was poor. The results of the study also showed that the importance of the school environment ranged from high to medium. Also that the means related to fostering the culture of dialog in the school environment ranged from low to high.

Another study to wrap up with was held by Al-Mizer (2017), which aimed at identifying the role of family in promoting a culture of dialog. In order to achieve this aim, a social survey was applied on a purposively selected sample of 253 subject from the Ministry of Education in Riyadh_Saudi Arabia, and a questionnaire which measured three dimensions to achieve the overall goal of the study. The results showed that the first dimension for learning the basics of dialog in the Saudi family ranked high. The main challenges presented by the findings included: The attachment to social networks and the intolerance to criticism during dialog. The study also revealed that the third dimension which is related to the proposals that may enhance the practice of dialog fundamentals within the Saudi family ranked high. To further enrich the study, a set of suggestions to promote a culture of dialog within the Saudi family were recommended, such as: Inculcating the principles of dialog within children at the very young, and

Table 1. The distribution of sample members according to each variable

Variable	Level	Number	%
Sex	Male	73	0.49
	Female	77	0.51
Scientific Experience	Less than 5 years	50	0.33
	From 5 to 10 years	48	0.32
	10 years	52	0.35
Total		150	100

encouraging families to run effective dialogs.

Comments on previous studies

A number of previous studies on the role of school leaders in promoting a culture of dialog among students were presented to enrich the theoretical framework of this study and to help in building a study tool for collecting data, to explore some statistical methods and to interpret the results of this study.

These studies were conducted in different times and held different goals and outcomes.

This study is recognized as the first in Al-Ras _within the researcher's knowledge _ on the role of school leaders in promoting a culture of dialog. It was characterized by its analysis and its results.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method

The descriptive approach was adopted to fit the objectives of the study.

Study Community

The school community is composed of all the school leaders in Al-Ras region during the first semester of the year 2019-2020, exactly (206) member.

Study Sample: Primary schools leaders

The sample is chosen in a relatively random mode, which has a number of (150). Table (1) provides the distribution of the sample according to the variables sex and scientific experience:

Research Tools

After reviewing the literature and presenting previous studies on the subject of the study, a questionnaire was

developed to investigate the role of school leaders in promoting a culture of dialog. The questionnaire was unfolded into two areas (dialog values enhancement, dialog skills acquisition) in addition to a sum of 31 paragraph which were also collected.

Research Tool Accuracy

After the initial questionnaire was designed, it was distributed to a group of 10 judges, specialists and faculty members in the faculty of education in Saudi universities. The judges were asked to estimate the quality of the contents of paragraphs and the language form and accuracy, the appropriateness of the paragraph for the area under which it is included, as well as any other views that they may consider appropriate, be it deletion, addition or integration. The judges ended up with several observations. They amended some paragraphs which were agreed upon by more than 80% of the them.

Research Tool Stability

To verify the stability of the study tool, the Pearson's association coefficients between the results of the two applications were calculated, ranging from the stability parameters of the two domains (0.89 -0.90). While the correlation coefficient reached (0.91), which was appropriate to the study's objectives.

Research Tool Correction

The five-tonal Likert scale for approval scores was used as follows: Very large (5), large (4), average (3), low (2), and very little (1), to estimate the role of school leaders in promoting the culture of dialog among primary school students in Al-Ras district. The following statistical scale has been used to distribute the means, as follows:

Period	04	
Length of Interval	=	0.80
Number of (5-1) intervals		

Table 2. The means and standard deviations of the estimates of schools leaders

Rank	Number	Area	Mean	Standard Deviation	Role scale
1	2	Dialog Skills Aquisition	3.37	0.71	Moderate
2	1	Dialog Values Enhancement	3.33	0.76	Moderate
The role of school leaders in promoting the culture of dialog			3.35	0.75	moderate

Ps: The Highest scale is 5.

The distribution of categories, thus, became as follows:

First: (1-1.80) very minimal role.

Second: (1.81-2.60) a minimal role.

Third: (2.61-3.40) a moderate role.

Fourth: (3.41-4.20) a significant role.

Fifth: (4.21-5.00) a very significant role.

Study Variables

Independant variables

Sex: two categories (male and female).

Experience: three levels (less than 5 years, from 5 years to under 10 years, 10 years or more).

Dependent variable

The role of school leaders in promoting a culture of dialog among students in Al-Ras school district.

Statistical Processing

The researcher used the following statistical treatment:

* to answer *Question 1*, the means and standard deviations of the study sample estimates were relied upon, the t- test was used, together with the One Way ANOVA.

RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

QUESTION 1: What role do school leaders play in prompting the culture of dialog among primary school students in Al-Ras district from the perspective of school leaders?"

To answer this question, the means and standard deviations of the estimates of school leaders were calculated. Table (2) displays that.

Table (2) displays that the area of 'dialog skills' ranked first with a mean of (3.37), a standard deviation of (0.71) occupying a moderate role. While the area of 'dialog values enhancement' came second with a mean of (3.33) and a standard deviation of (0.76) and a moderate role.

As far as the role of school leaders in promoting the culture of dialog is concerned, the mean of the sample population estimates was (3.35), with a standard deviation of (0.75), occupying a moderate role. This may be attributed to the lack of interest among school leaders in activating activities parallel to the curriculum that promote a culture of dialog among students. They have little follow-up to teachers to activate their role in fostering a culture of dialog among students. The results of this study are consistent with the Zahrani Study (2011), which shows that the level of dialog culture among the educational supervisors from the standpoint of each aspect of the dialog was of a moderate level. But they differ from the results of Al Jabreen's (2016) response, which indicated that promoting a culture of dialog among students in the school environment is low.

The means and standard deviations of school leaders' estimates were calculated in the all the areas related to the role of school leaders in promoting the culture of dialog, as follows:

Area I: Dialog Values Development

The means and standard deviations of school leaders' estimates in promoting a culture of dialog were calculated as shown in table (3):

Table (3) shows that paragraph 11, which tackles "developing the value of national affiliation of students during the dialog", ranked first with a mean of (3.70) and a standard deviation of (0.90) with a high scale. The second paragraph, which talks about "developing the value of modesty among students during the dialog", came second with a mean of (3.51), a standard deviation of (1.00) and a high scale. While paragraph (16), which discusses "developing the value of modesty among students during the dialog", was the last with a mean of (3.05) and a standard deviation of (0.89) and a moderate degree.

The sample population estimates marked a mean of (3.33) and a standard deviation of (0.85), with a moderate scale. This result may be attributed to a number of school leaders following the dictatorial style of administration, which is in fact reflected on the dialog and its values. Consequently the failure of dialog is because the dictatorial leader cancels the other's role in talking. This leads to a failure to develop the values of dialog such as acceptance of the other opinion, self-control

Table 3. The means and standard deviations for the estimates of the paragraphs according to the area of *Dialog Values Development*

Rank	Number	Paragraphs	Mean	Standard Deviation	Role Rank
1	11	Developing the value of national affiliation among students during the dialog.	3.70	0.90	high
2	2	Developing the value of modesty among students during the dialog	3.51	1.00	high
3	1	Developing the value of accepting other opinions among students during the dialog	3.52	0.91	high
4	12	Developing the value of the transparency in presentation among students during the dialog	3.48	1.02	high
5	7	Developing the value of patience and self-restraint in studentstalk situations	3.42	1.01	high
6	5	Developing the value of disciplineamong students during the dialog	3.38	1.03	moderate
7	3	Developing the value of objectivity among students during the dialog	3.37	1.15	moderate
7	9	Developing the value of pride of the Islamic identity among during dialog.	3.36	0.96	moderate
7	17	Developing the value of compassion among students during the dialog.	3.35	1.06	moderate
10	10	Developing the value of student self-confidence during the dialog.	3.33	0.93	moderate
11	15	Developing the value invoking for justice among students during the dialog.	3.26	0.95	moderate
11	13	Developing the value of the transparencywhen quoting among students during dialog.	3.26	0.94	moderate
13	4	Developing the value of validating information during students' dialogs	3.17	0.95	moderate
14	6	Developing the value of student cooperation during the dialog.	3.16	0.98	moderate
14	14	Develop the value of tolerance towards the students who disagree during the dialog.	3.16	0.98	moderate
16	8	Developing the value of respect among students during the dialog	3.14	0.97	moderate
17	16	Developing the value of kindness to during among students during dialog	3.05	0.89	moderate
Total Area			3.33	0.85	

Ps: the highest scale is 5.

during the talk, and other values that require a good example in order to be developed.

AREA II: Dialog SkillsAcquisition

The means and standard deviations of school leaders' estimates in promoting a culture of dialog were calculated on the elements of this area, as shown in table (4):

Table(4) shows that paragraph (26), which tackles "*Teachingstudents the skill of flexible thinking during a dialog*", ranked first with a mean of (3.64), a standard deviation of (0.93) with a high scale. On the other hand, paragraph (31), which tackles "*teaching students logical progression skill during dialog*", came second with a mean of (3.61), a standard deviation of

(1.09) with a high scale. while paragraph (19), which was about "*teaching students the skill of fluency in speech during dialog*", ranked last with a mean of (2.82), a standard deviation of (1.04) marking a moderate scale. While the sample population estimates for the sections of this area as a whole had a mean of(3.37) and standard deviation of (0.74) and marked as moderate. This could be justified by the heavy administrative burden on school leaders and work pressures, which leaves no chance for them to pursue developing students' dialog skillsand urge teachers to use the means and methods that develop students' dialog skills. Thus, the role of school leaders in promoting a culture of dialog in bringing students to dialog skills did not match the required level. The results of this study differ from the Al-Juhaimi Study (2013), which emphasized that the general average practice of dialog runned by Shariaa sciences teachers with their

Table 4. Means and standard deviations of school leaders' estimates according to the paragraphs of the area of dialog skills acquisition

Rank	Number	Paragraph	Mean	Standard Deviation	Role Scale
01	26	Teaching students flexible thinking skills during dialog	3.74	0.99	High
02	31	Teaching students logical progression skill during dialog	3.62	1.07	High
03	21	Training the students on the skill of clarity in expressing their point of view during the dialog.	3.53	0.94	High
03	27	Equipping students with the skill of identifying the problem of dialog.	3.52	0.98	High
03	30	Familiarizing students with the skill of determining the areas of agreement and disagreement.	3.52	0.91	High
06	24	Familiarizing the students with the skill of prioritization in the dialog.	3.50	0.93	High
07	22	Teaching students the skill of changing the voice tone in dialogs.	3.39	1.06	Moderate
08	25	Developing students' nonverbal communication skills during the dialog.	3.32	0.89	Moderate
09	29	Equipping students the skill of analyzing and scrutinating evidence during the dialog.	3.26	1.04	Moderate
10	23	Teaching students the skill of influencing others during the dialog.	3.23	1.15	Moderate
11	20	Developing the skill of selecting the appropriate words during the dialog	3.23	1.13	Moderate
12	18	Making students aware of the skill of self-control during the dialog.	3.15	1.13	Moderate
13	28	Training students on the skill of being able to express different possibilities during the dialog.	3.14	1.09	Moderate
14	19	Helping students to have the skill of fluency in speech during the dialog.	2.82	1.04	Moderate
Area			3.37	0.74	Moderate

PS : The highest scale :05

Table 5. The results of the t-test of differences in role by sex

Area	Sex	Mean	Standard deviation	t- value	Degree of freedom	Statistical significance
Dialog skills acquisition	male	3.21	0.89	0.63	148	*0.00
	female	3.50	0.93			
Dialog values development	male	3.25	0.81	2.224	148	*0.011
	female	3.45	0.85			

Ps: the differences are statistically significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

students came weak in the area of *dialog skills acquisition*.

QUESTION 02: Do the estimates of the sample of the study on promoting a culture of dialog among primary students in Al-Ras region vary by the variables (gender, experience)?

To answer this question, the sample population's means and standard deviations were calculated on the areas in which school leaders play a role in promoting a culture of dialog among students according to the

variables: *gender* and *experience*.

Differences by sex

A t-test was used on the sample in order to test the differences in the role by sex (male and female leaders) . Table (5) shows this:

The t-test results indicate statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) concerning the study sample subjects' estimates based on the variable of sex and in

Table 6. The means of the role by experience

Area	Stage	Mean	Standard deviation
Dialogskills aquisition	Less than 5 years	3.33	0.92
	From 5 to 10 years	3.35	0.89
	10 years or more	3.37	0.86
Dialog values development	Less than 5 years	3.31	0.83
	From 5 to 10 years	3.34	0.85
	10 years or more	3.38	0.73

Table 7. The results of analysis of variance – ANOVA off the differences in role test

Area		Source of variance	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean squares	F value calculated	statistical significance
Dialogue aquisition	skills	Between Groups	0.586	2	0.293	0.355	0.452
		Within Groups (Error)	725.361	147	0.827		
		Total	725.948	149			
Dialog development	values	Between Groups	0.919	2	0.459	0.669	0.313
		Within Groups (Error)	602.442	147	0.687		
		Total	603.361	149			

Ps: the results are statistically significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

favor of female school leaders. This may be due to the fact that female leaders practice dialog and enhance the dialog culture with their female students, for they are more patient and more reflective in their nature and due to the quality of motherhood they carry. The reflection of this on the educational process and the inculcation of the culture of dialog in the behavior of students is clear. The results of this study are consistent with the study of Sukr (2013), which emphasized statistically significant differences between the mean of the sample estimates concerning the role of the teaching staff in promoting a culture of dialog attributed to the gender variable in favor of females. However, they differ from the study results of Al-jararia (2012) which showed that there are no statistically significant differences in the practice of the culture of dialog attributed to *gender* as a variable.

Differences by experience

The One Way ANOVA was used by testing the differences according to the variable of experience. Table (6) shows this:

Table (7) shows the differences in means. To test the significance of differences, the One Way ANOVA was used. The results show that there are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) among the sample

population estimates' means on the areas of school leaders role in promoting the culture of dialog among students at the school and the tool as a whole. This result may be justified by the fact that dialog is a culture that must be rooted within the school leaders and within all the aspects of the learning process; therefore, the culture of dialog was mediocre among all the school members, regardless to experience. This also indicates that despite the fact that the culture of dialog is practiced by all school leaders, yet it is carried out with no competition neither promotion. The results of this study happen to be consistent with the Baskas' (2010) study, which showed that there are no differences in the management of the dialog due to the variable of experience.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The Department of Education should focus on dialog and its manners in teaching among leaders and students as well as among leaders and all members of the educational process
2. More training courses should be dedicated to school leaders focusing on using the proper methodology for a sound dialog.
3. Further studies in all the Kingdom regions are recom-

mended to energize the dialog method in the education process.

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